

Combined toxicity of perfluoroalkyl substances and microplastics on the sentinel species *Daphnia magna*: Implications for freshwater ecosystems[☆]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

PFAS
Microplastics
Waterflea
Chronic toxicity
Chemical mixtures
Developmental failure

ABSTRACT

Persistent chemicals from industrial processes, particularly perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), have become pervasive in the environment due to their persistence, long half-lives, and bioaccumulative properties. Used globally for their thermal resistance and repellence to water and oil, PFAS have led to widespread environmental contamination. These compounds pose significant health risks with exposure through food, water, and dermal contact. Aquatic wildlife is particularly vulnerable as water bodies act as major transport and transformation mediums for PFAS. Their co-occurrence with microplastics may intensify the impact on aquatic species by influencing PFAS sorption and transport. Despite progress in understanding the occurrence and fate of PFAS and microplastics in aquatic ecosystems, the toxicity of PFAS mixtures and their co-occurrence with other high-concern compounds remains poorly understood, especially over organisms' life cycles.

Our study investigates the chronic toxicity of PFAS and microplastics on the sentinel species *Daphnia*, a species central to aquatic foodwebs and an ecotoxicology model. We examined the effects of perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), and polyethylene terephthalate microplastics (PET) both individually and in mixtures on *Daphnia* ecological endpoints. Unlike conventional studies, we used two *Daphnia* genotypes with distinct histories of chemical exposure. This approach revealed that PFAS and microplastics cause developmental failures, delayed sexual maturity and reduced somatic growth, with historical exposure to environmental pollution reducing tolerance to these persistent chemicals due to cumulative fitness costs. We also observed that the combined effect of the persistent chemicals analysed was 59% additive and 41% synergistic, whereas no antagonistic interactions were observed. The genotype-specific responses observed highlight the complex interplay between genetic background and pollutant exposure, emphasizing the importance of incorporating multiple genotypes in environmental risk assessments to more accurately predict the ecological impact of chemical pollutants.

1. Introduction

Persistent chemicals from domestic and industrial processes have become ubiquitous in the environment due to their long half-lives, recalcitrant nature, and bioaccumulative properties (Buck et al.,

2011). Among these, perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are increasingly detected in soil, sediment, and water at concentrations ranging from picograms to nanograms per litre (Mojiri et al., 2023). PFAS are synthetic chemicals used globally in industrial applications such as metal plating, aqueous film-forming foams, and in paper and textiles. Their

[☆] This paper has been recommended for acceptance by Dr Jiayin Dai.

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thermal resistance and repellence to water and oil make them valuable for industrial and consumer products, including food packaging, cookware, upholstery, water-resistant clothing, and personal care products (Jane et al., 2022). The economic value of PFAS in 2023 exceeded \$28 billion, reflecting their extensive use in both commercial and residential applications and a significant increase from \$1 billion market size in 2006 (Chemsec, 2023; Prevedouros et al., 2006).

Due to their widespread use, PFAS are released into the environment during manufacturing, distribution, use, and disposal. Their high persistence and bioaccumulative properties enable global transport through air, water, and land, leading to their detection even in remote locations such as the Arctic and Antarctic regions (Pozo et al., 2017; Vecchiato et al., 2015). Since the discovery of PFAS in Arctic wildlife tissue at the turn of the 21st century (Kumar et al., 2002) and later in human blood (Sunderland et al., 2019), these chemicals have become substances of very high concern. Recent regulations on PFAS have tightened significantly. In 2024, the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) banned PFAS from new production processes, with 13 states adopting the regulation (EPA, 2024). New limits for perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) in drinking water are set at 4 ng/L (USEPA, 2024). In the EU, the European Commission's 2020 Chemicals Strategy aimed to phase out PFAS, while the European Parliament set a drinking water limit of 0.5 µg/L in 2019 (OECD, 2019), classifying PFAS as compound of very high concern (OECD, 2023). The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) recommends a total weekly intake of no more than 4.4 ng/kg of body weight (Schrenk et al., 2020; Commission, 2020; EPA, 2024; OECD, 2019; 2023; USEPA, 2024). Despite these measures, the decades-long use of PFAS and their persistence in the environment mean that a significant proportion of the global population is currently and will continue to be exposed to levels exceeding recommended limits.

Humans are exposed to PFAS through food, water, occupation, and the environment (Crawford et al., 2023). Known adverse effects of PFAS include cancer, immune system dysfunction, cardiovascular issues, and developmental problems such as low birth weight (Crawford et al., 2023; van Gerwen et al., 2023). Drinking water accounts for up to 14% of exposure to PFOA and 10% to PFOS, while diet accounts for up to 40% of exposure to PFAS in adults (Hu et al., 2016; Sunderland et al., 2019).

The aquatic environment is the compartment more susceptible to PFAS because it serves as a major transport and transformation medium, particularly for PFAS with high water solubility, such as ionic PFAS (Ahrens and Bundschuh, 2014). Despite regulatory restrictions and the mandatory phase-out of long-chain PFAS, these compounds continue to enter aquatic systems from the degradation of PFAS precursors and from historical products still in use. These sources can remobilize PFAS into the water from soil, sediment, and ice (Ahrens, 2011). Additionally, emissions of other PFAS, particularly short-chain PFAS, are on the rise. Short-chain PFAS are more mobile in aquatic environments, while long-chain PFAS, which are more hydrophobic, tend to bind to particles. PFOS and PFOA are the most frequently detected PFAS in freshwater ecosystems and have been shown to exert toxic effects on freshwater organisms (Ahrens, 2011; Ahrens and Bundschuh, 2014; Wang et al., 2023). Typically, PFOS is found in higher concentrations and is more toxic than PFOA to aquatic species, as evidenced by acute toxicity tests (Ji et al., 2008; Mojiri et al., 2023).

The impact of PFAS is exacerbated by the presence of other persistent compounds, such as microplastics (MP), which can facilitate their sorption (Bhagwat et al., 2021). The enhanced toxicity of MP for other persistent contaminants, including PFAS, can be mediated by biofilm formation, which intensifies the vector role of MP (Qi et al., 2021). Biofilms can also bioconcentrate PFAS in freshwater environments (Munoz et al., 2018), and alter their transport and transformation (Dai et al., 2022). Additionally, MP and PFAS are often released simultaneously from consumer products, such as waterproof textiles, further exacerbating their environmental impact (Kang et al., 2023).

Despite significant progress in understanding the occurrence and fate

of PFAS and MP in aquatic ecosystems, the toxicity of PFAS mixtures and their co-occurrence with other high-concern pollutants remains poorly understood, especially over organisms' life cycles (Mojiri et al., 2023). Few in vitro studies have investigated mixture effects, primarily focusing on PFAS mixtures (e.g. (Ding et al., 2013)). These studies revealed that mixtures can exert higher toxic effects than individual compounds, showing additive or synergistic effects depending on mixture components, target species, and dose ratios (Garvey et al., 2023; Ojo et al., 2021). While the combined effects of PFOS and PFOA have been empirically studied in human cell lines (Hu and Hu, 2009), fish, birds, and mammals (Suja et al., 2009), most research relies on models such as concentration addition and independent action (Escher et al., 2020). These models, which assume no interactions in the analysed mixtures, may overestimate or underestimate the combined toxic effects of interacting chemicals. The scarcity of empirical studies on these combined effects can lead to inaccurate risk assessments. This study aims to address this gap by using the sentinel and keystone species *Daphnia*, a well-established ecotoxicology model, which is used to define safe concentrations of chemicals in the environment (Abdullahi et al., 2022a).

Daphnia is central to freshwater food webs, making it an ecologically relevant species (Abdullahi et al., 2022a; Altschuler et al., 2011). With an exceptionally long dormancy, *Daphnia* allows us to access past populations with different exposure histories to environmental pollutants (Cuenca Cambronero and Orsini, 2018). Capitalizing on these properties, we assessed the chronic toxicity of PFOS, PFOA, and polyethylene terephthalate (PET), both as single chemicals and in mixtures, on two genotypes of *Daphnia* resurrected from the sedimentary archives of Lake Ring, Denmark. This lake has a well-documented history of anthropogenic impact over the past century (Cuenca Cambronero et al., 2018). One genotype originated from a semi-pristine environment and is naïve to chemical pollution, while the other had been exposed to chemical pollution for multiple sexual generations, referred to as 'experienced' hereunder (Abdullahi et al., 2022b).

We used irregular microplastic, including fibers and fragments, which closely represent MP in the natural environment, and environmentally relevant concentrations of PFOS and PFOA, two commonly co-occurring PFAS in water (Ding et al., 2013). While single PFAS have previously been shown to impair growth in *Daphnia*, our study is the first to investigate the combined effects of these chemicals, providing a comprehensive understanding of the chronic toxicity of two-way and three-way mixtures of high-concern chemicals that co-occur in freshwater environments. Given *Daphnia*'s central role in freshwater food webs, our findings have potential implications for the entire freshwater community, including primary producers and consumers of *Daphnia*.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study system

The *Daphnia magna* genotypes used in this study were previously revived from a biological archive of Lake Ring, Denmark (55° 57' 51.83" N, 9° 35' 46.87" E), a shallow mixed lake with a well-documented history of anthropogenic impact over the past century (Cuenca Cambronero et al., 2018). The lake was semi-pristine between the 1900s and 1950s (semi-pristine phase; SP); it experienced high levels of eutrophication from the 1950s to the 1970s (eutrophic phase; EP). From the 1980s to the 1990s, the lake suffered from pesticides inflow (1980–1990; pesticide phase; PP). In modern times the lake experienced a partial recovery from eutrophication but still received some agricultural run-off (Recovery Phase; RP) (Cuenca Cambronero et al., 2018; Eastwood et al., 2023). Two *D. magna* genotypes, one from the pristine and one from the recovery phases were used in this study. These were chosen to assess the compounded effect of prior exposure to chemical pollutants on the tolerance to modern chemical pollutants, namely PFOS, PFOA and PET. This was done by comparing the impact of each of these chemicals and

their two-ways and three-ways mixtures on the fitness of the naïve (LR1136_1) and the experienced genotype (LRV0_1) in common garden experiments following [Abdullahi et al. \(2022b\)](#). The concentrations of chemicals tested were within the range of environmentally relevant concentrations, especially for PFOS and PFOA ([Ahrens, 2011](#); [Mojiri et al., 2023](#)).

2.2. Characterization of contaminants

PET granules (Sigma -Aldrich, USA; density = 1.68×10^{12} ng/L; CAS No 25038-59-9) were cryogenically grounded in liquid nitrogen in a Freezer/Mill 6775 (United States), SPEX SamplePrep to obtain irregularly shaped particles. These were size selected with stainless steel filters to retain particles between 38 μm and 50 μm , easily ingestible by *Daphnia*. Following the grounding process, the PET particles were characterized using both microscopy and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS; Malvern Nano Series Zetasizer). A concentrated solution of 1 mg/ml of PET was examined using a Digital Optika™ IM-3LD4D ProView, Italy) microscope with multiple lenses Plan Fluor (4X, 10X, 20X, 40X). Visualisation and measurements of MPs were conducted using the bespoke “Optika™ ProView Image Analysis” software for the built-in 6.3megapixel USB 3.0 CMOS digital camera. The average size and shape of the particles used in the experiment were determined based on the analysis of 300 randomly selected particles. A concentrated solution of PET particles (1 mg/ml) was transferred to three replicated glass petri dishes for microscopic observations. Up to 100 fragments and fibers were randomly selected from each plate, equally split among the four quadrants of each plate. The selected MP were sized using the Optika™ ProView Image Analysis software. To confirm the size and surface charge of the MP, 5 mL solutions of 2×10^9 ng/L of PET were prepared and subjected to analysis using Dynamic Light Scattering). Subsequently, four replicates of 1 mL aliquots of the solution were tested on the DLS to determine average particle size, zeta potential, and polydispersity index.

The nominal concentration of PFOS and PFOA in single chemical and mixture exposures were respectively 70 ng/L and 7 ng/L. We used concentrations that reflect the ones observed in lakes, where PFOS occurs at typically higher concentrations than PFOA in Europe (PFOS average concentration: <100 ng/L; PFOA average concentration: <10 ng/L) ([Ahrens, 2011](#)). Before exposing *Daphnia* to these chemicals, we quantified medium spiked with the experimental concentrations to confirm the chemicals nominal concentrations. Media spiked with PFOS and PFOA was subjected to Solid Phase Extraction followed by LC-MS/MS (Shimadzu LC-20AB prominence high pressure liquid Chromatography: Shimadzu Kyoto, Japan) analysis according to a previously published method ([Abdullahi et al., 2023](#); [Harrad et al., 2019](#)) and after filtering out MP particles from mixtures. Briefly, the cartridges used for the extraction were first conditioned with 6 mL of methanol (0.1% NH_4OH) and rinsed with 6 mL of Milli-Q water. The internal (surrogate) standards used were M8PFOA + M8 (1 ng/ μL) and the recovery determination standard was M4PFOS (1 ng/ μL) (Wellington Laboratories). Duplicate samples per single chemical and mixtures were analysed and quantified on LC-MS/MS, coupled with a Sciex API 2000mass Spectrometer (Applied biosystems Foster City, CA, USA) ([Abdullahi et al., 2023](#); [Harrad et al., 2019](#)).

All experiments were conducted in glass jars, following strict QA/QC protocols. To minimise background contamination by MP and PFAS in the laboratory, researchers wore pure cotton lab coats and nitrile gloves. Furthermore, all sample processing took place on a laminar flow bench, which was regularly wiped with 90% ethanol. Laboratory equipment and consumables were rinsed with Milli-Q water prior to use. Samples were processed in batches of five, with a ‘method blank’ (Milli-Q water in a clean glass bottle) included in each batch to monitor potential contamination during sample preparation. Additionally, a ‘recovery sample’ (Milli-Q water spiked with a known quantity of MP/PFAS) was analysed for each 20 samples to assess recovery rates and background

interference. A ‘field blank’, consisting of experimental medium without MP/PFAS, was also included with every 20 samples to check for contamination from the medium or laboratory.

2.3. Assessing the chronic toxicity of single chemicals and mixtures

The toxicity of PFOS (70 ng/L), PFOA (7 ng/L), PET (50 mg/L) and their two-way and three-way mixtures were tested on the two *Daphnia* genotypes for the duration of their life cycles (until they released their second brood) ([Fig. 1](#)). To ensure a homogeneous PET solution, a stock solution of 5 g/L was prepared and gently stirred on a magnetic stirrer before dosing the experimental vials at 50 mg/L.

Before the chronic toxicity test, we performed a qualitative assessment of *Daphnia*'s ingestion and egestion of microplastic over 72h. We exposed three clonal replicates of the two genotypes used subsequently in the chronic toxicity tests to 50 mg/L of PET over 72h. Ingestion of microplastics was monitored every 24h in absence of feed. This experiment was run alongside a control in which *Daphnia* were fed algae. After 72h, *Daphnia* was transferred to clean medium every 24h, to visualise egestion of PET by microscope imaging. All images were captured using J software ([Rueden et al., 2017](#)). The medium was renewed every 24 h and up to 72h after the last PET ingestion to estimate the gut retention time of PET and the time to full egestion.

Clonal replicates of the two genotypes were obtained from the stock collection of the University of Birmingham where they are maintained in standard laboratory conditions: 16:8-hr light–dark photoperiod; 0.8 mg/L of *Chlorella vulgaris* fed weekly; ambient temperature: 10 °C ([Cuenca Cambronero et al., 2018](#)). The growth medium used was borehole water, collected from a deep aquifer well and showing stable physico-chemical properties. Before commencing the exposures, clonal replicates of the two genotypes were acclimated in common garden conditions for three generations to the following conditions to reduce interference from maternal effects and synchronize reproduction: 16:8-hr light–dark photoperiod; 0.8 mg/L of *C. vulgaris* fed daily; ambient temperature: 20 ± 2 °C. After three generations in these conditions, 24-hr-old randomly selected juveniles from the second or following broods were assigned to experimental conditions.

A total of 64 exposures were completed, including seven treatments and one control group for both genotypes and four clonal replicates per genotype and condition ([Fig. 1](#)). During the experiment, the growth medium (borehole water) was replenished every other day and spiked with the same concentration of chemical at each medium change to ensure a constant exposure throughout the experiment. Fitness-linked life history traits were measured during the experiment covering the *Daphnia*'s life cycle (until release of the second brood): age at maturity (first time the parthenogenetic eggs are released in the brood pouch); size at maturity (distance from the head to the base of the tail spine); fecundity (number of juveniles across the first two broods); interval between broods (days between the first and second brood) and mortality. Size was measured after the release of the second brood using ImageJ open-source software ([Rueden et al., 2017](#)).

2.4. Statistical analyses

Univariate reaction norms were used to assess the effect of genotype (G), treatment (T -PFOS; PFOA; PET; PET + PFOA; PET + PFOS; PFOA + PFOS; PET + PFOA + PFOS) and their interaction terms (G x T) on the five fitness-linked life history traits (age at maturity, size at maturity, fecundity, interval between broods and mortality) using a two-way ANOVA. A linear mixed effect model (LMMs) was used with clonal replicates nested within genotype using the “lmerTest” package in R version 4.3.1 ([Kuznetsova et al., 2017](#)). Before applying the LMMs model, the data were checked for normality using the Q-Q plots (residual vs. fitted values) ([Zuur et al., 2010](#)).

The main effects of treatment, genotype and their interactions were visualized using reaction norm plots. The mortality rate per treatment

Fig. 1. Experimental design. Populations separated in time of *Daphnia magna* were previously resurrected from a sedimentary archive of Lake Ring (Denmark). The lake experienced four phases due to environmental impact. A genotype from the pristine (black) and one from the recovery phase (ref) of the lake were used in this study to assess the impact of PFOS (70 ng/L); PFOA (7 ng/L); PET (50 mg/L) and two-way and tree-way mixtures on *Daphnia*'s ecological endpoints.

and genotype was estimated with the survival model fit using the `psm` function in the “rms” package in R version 3.6.0 (Harrell Jr, 2023). The day of mortality and mortality events were combined as a response variable while the term *genotype* was treated as a fixed effect. The mortality curves were plotted with the `survplot` function from the `rms` package in R v.6.7.1 (Harrell Jr, 2023). A separate model was fitted to each treatment.

Effects on the overall fitness were calculated using multivariate statistics (MANOVA) by combining the life history traits (age at maturity, size at maturity, fecundity, and interval between broods) as response variables (y) whilst treatment and genotype were fixed terms ($y \sim \text{treatment} * \text{genotype}$). As per the ANOVA analysis of individual fitness-linked life history traits, a linear mixed effect model (LMMs) was used with clonal replicates nested within genotype using the “lmerTest” package in R version 4.3.1 (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). The multivariate reaction norms were visualized using the phenotypic trajectory analysis (PTA) plots to describe the difference between control and treatments in terms of magnitude and direction of change following Adams and Collyer (2009).

2.5. Mixture effects

In the common garden experiments, we investigated whether the two-way and three-way combinations of the chemical mixtures exhibited synergistic, antagonistic, or additive effects on *Daphnia* fitness-linked life history traits. To assess this, we used a null model of additivity (Cote et al., 2016), which contrasts the expected additive effect of two or more compounds (i.e., the sum of each compound individual effects) on fitness linked life history traits with the empirical observed

effect of mixtures. These inferences were possible because the same set of genotypes was exposed to the single chemicals and the mixtures. The null additive prediction of the joint effect of stressors combinations was calculated as:

$$E_{\text{mix}} = EA + EB + EC$$

where EA, EB and EC are the effects of single compounds and E_{mix} is the mixtures effect. For each trait ‘y’ (age at maturity, size at maturity, fecundity, and interval between broods), standardized effect sizes were used corresponding to $(y_{\text{treatment}} - y_{\text{control}}) / \sigma$, where σ is the shared standard deviation of the pooled control and treatment trait values per treatment following (Cote et al., 2016). This analysis could not be done on mortality because individuals killed by one chemical cannot be killed by another simultaneously and, hence, the additive model does not apply to this trait. The effect of mixtures was considered additive if the predicted joint effect ‘ E_{mix} ’ was within the 95% confidence intervals of the observed effect from the multiple stressors and not significantly different from the null model. The effect of multiple stressors was antagonistic if the predicted joint effect was significantly smaller of the null model and synergistic if the predicted joint effect was significantly larger than the null model. We used a Welch Two sample *t*-test to assess significant departure from the null model. This test compares the means of the predicted null model and the empirical observed values for each fitness-linked life-history trait.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of chemicals

Results from blanks and recovery samples for both PET and PFAS are in Table S1. None of the blank concentrations exceeded 5% of the average PET count or PFAS concentration in their respective sample batches, so no blank correction was necessary. Recovery of spiked MPs and PFAS ranged from 79% to 117%, demonstrating good analytical performance (Table S1).

The microscopic observation and DLS, used to confirm physico-chemical properties, size and surface charge of the PET particles revealed that 33% of the particles were fibers with an average size of 20.03 μm , and 67% were fragments with an average size of 14.93 μm (Tables S2 and S3). The DLS analysis showed that the PET particles were negatively charged, and that the zeta potential (electrophoretic mobility of particles in an ionic solution) was -46.4 mV. The size intensity was 132.1 (d.nm). The fibers size ranged between 7.23 μm and 54.72 μm , whereas the fragment size ranged between 8.93 μm and 45.91 (Table S1; Fig. S1). The bioaccessible concentrations of PFOS and PFOA in the media were confirmed with LC-MS/MS to not depart from the nominal concentrations (Table S3).

3.2. Assessing the chronic toxicity of single chemicals and mixtures

The preliminary experiment assessing the ingestion and egestion capacity of PET particles in *Daphnia* showed that the organisms could ingest and retain the particles for up to 72 h. Once transferred to a microplastic-free medium, their guts were emptied within 24 h (Fig. S2).

We studied the effects of single, two-way and three-way mixtures of PFOS, PFOA and PET on *Daphnia* fitness-linked life-history traits (Fig. 1). Exposures to PET, PFOS and PFOA as single chemicals had a significant treatment effect (Table 1, MANOVA; Fig. 2). This overall response for PET was driven by a significantly smaller size at maturity, lower fecundity, longer interval between broods and higher mortality in the exposed *Daphnia* (Table 1, ANOVA; Fig. 3 PET; Fig. S3). The response to PFOA was driven by a delay in sexual maturity, smaller size at maturity, reduced fecundity and longer interval between broods in the exposed *Daphnia* (Table 1, ANOVA; Fig. 2, PFOA). No mortality was observed in exposures to PFOA (Fig. S3). In addition to a treatment effect, PFOS also induced a significant different response between genotypes (Table 1, MANOVA; Fig. 2, PFOA). For this treatment, we observed a significantly smaller size at maturity, lower fecundity, longer interval between broods and higher mortality in exposed *Daphnia*; in addition, age at maturity, interval between broods and mortality significantly differed between genotypes (Table 1, ANOVA; Fig. 3, PFOS; Fig. S3). No significant interaction effects (GxT) were observed in the single chemical exposures (Table 1; MANOVA).

Whereas all chemical mixtures showed a significant treatment effect, genotypes responded differently to PET + PFOA and PFOA + PFOS; in these treatments, a significant interaction term (GxT) was found, indicating a genotype dependent response to treatment (Table 1, MANOVA; Fig. 2). The individual life-history traits contributing to these patterns differed among treatments. In the PET + PFOA, we observed a genotype dependent response in age and size at maturity and a response to treatment of the individual life history traits largely reflecting the patterns observed in the respective single stress exposures (Table 1, ANOVA; Fig. 3; PET + PFOA). *Daphnia* exposed to PET + PFOS had significantly smaller size at maturity, lower fecundity, longer interval between broods, but did not experience mortality, with a significant genotype dependent response for age at maturity (Table 1, ANOVA; Fig. 3; PET + PFOS; Fig. S3). The combination of PFOS and PFOA caused a smaller size at maturity, lower fecundity and longer interval between broods (Table 1, ANOVA, Fig. 3; PFOS + PFOA). This treatment also showed a genotype dependent response in size at maturity and interval between broods (Table 1, ANOVA, Fig. 3; PFOS + PFOA). Reduced

number of offspring was paired with developmental failure resulting in a high number of aborted broods in the PFOS treatment (Fig. S4). Finally, the overall fitness response in the three-way chemical mixture was driven by a delayed maturity, smaller size at maturity and reduced fecundity; a genotype-dependent response was observed for size at maturity (Table 1, ANOVA, Fig. 3; PFOS + PFOA + PET). Mortality did not significantly increase in the two-way and three-way chemical mixture treatments as compared to controls (Fig. S3).

3.3. Mixture effects

We quantified the effect of two-way and three-way chemical mixtures on the life-history traits using an additive null model. Across the life history traits and treatments, interactions were 59% additive and 41% synergistic, with no recorded antagonistic interactions (Fig. 4, Table S4). The effect of combined stressors on age at maturity was 50% synergistic and 50% additive (Fig. 4, Table S4). The combined effect on size at maturity was 100% synergistic (Fig. 4, Table S4). The effect of multiple stressors on fecundity was 100% additive. The combined stressor effects on the interval between broods were 87.5% additive and 12.5% synergistic (Fig. 4, Table S4).

4. Discussion

4.1. Single chemicals effects

Our comprehension of the risks posed by persistent chemicals occurring at low concentrations in the environment is generally lacking, especially when they occur as mixtures (Abdullahi et al., 2022a; Jemec et al., 2016; Logeshwaran et al., 2021; Suppa et al., 2020). Understanding the chronic, long-term impact of these mixtures is critical considering that organisms' tolerance to persistent chemicals may be reduced by prior exposure to other environmental threats (Abdullahi et al., 2022a; Abdullahi et al., 2022b; Gigl et al., 2024). Our research addresses these crucial knowledge gaps by assessing the adverse effects of PFOS, PFOA, and PET as individual chemicals and mixtures on the life cycle of the sentinel species for ecotoxicology, *D. magna*. *Daphnia*, being a sensitive species, serves as a reliable indicator of the environmental risks associated with these persistent chemicals.

PFAS are recognized endocrine disruptors with impacts on ecosystems and humans (Negri et al., 2017; Sinclair et al., 2020; Suja et al., 2009). Existing studies have indicated that PFOS exhibits approximately ten times greater toxicity than PFOA in aquatic organisms, with variations depending on the study organism and whether acute or chronic toxicity were investigated (Ding et al., 2013; Ji et al., 2008). The observed adverse effects of PFAS on *Daphnia* are reduced reproduction and growth, and higher mortality (Jeong et al., 2016; Logeshwaran et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2015). In our study, both the reaction norms, supported by ANOVA analysis, and the effect size analysis comparing exposures between single chemicals and mixtures, corroborate impacts of PFOS and PFOA on *Daphnia*'s fitness-linked life history traits previously reported. However, a significant increase in mortality was observed only in individual exposures to PFOS. Previous studies indicating a higher toxicity of PFOS compared to PFOA were predominantly acute toxicity studies or employed concentrations of the two compounds that were above environmental relevance (>6 mg/L) (Logeshwaran et al., 2021). Notably, the fitness effects previously documented for PFOA and PFOS align well with our findings for exposures involving concentrations below 3 mg/L (Logeshwaran et al., 2021).

Although MPs are widely recognized as a modern threat to wildlife, their toxicity to aquatic species, particularly across the life cycles of organisms, remains poorly understood (An et al., 2021; Hodkovicova et al., 2022). Both marine and freshwater organisms are vulnerable to MP ingestion, with documented adverse effects ranging from lethal to sub-lethal outcomes (Avio et al., 2015; Cole et al., 2015; Green et al., 2016; Yin et al., 2023). These effects may result from a combination of

Table 1
 Analysis of variance. Multivariate (MANOVA) and univariate (ANOVA) analysis of variance, testing response of five fitness-linked life history traits to single chemicals and mixtures. The effect of treatment (T), genotype (G) and their interaction term (TxG) on the life history traits is shown. The life history traits assessed were age at maturity (days), size at maturity (mm), fecundity (number of offspring produced in the first two broods), interval between broods (days) and mortality. The chemicals tested are PET (50 mg/L), PFOA (7 ng/L), PFOS (70 ng/L) in isolation and combination. Significant *p*-values are shown in bold. na -no mortality occurred in the specific treatment.

	MANOVA			ANOVA														
	df	F	<i>p</i> -Value	Age at maturity (Day)			Size at maturity (mm)			Fecundity			Brood interval (Day)			Mortality		
				df	F	<i>p</i> -Value	df	F	<i>p</i> -Value	df	F	<i>p</i> -Value	df	F	<i>p</i> -Value	df	F	<i>p</i> -Value
PET																		
Treatment (T)	1	38.67	0.00	1	1.79	0.21	1	122.08	0.0002	1	155.64	0.0009	1	9.56	0.01	1	4.98	0.03
Genotype (G)	1	1.29	0.37	1	0.52	0.49	1	1.29	0.30	1	0.04	0.85	1	0.03	0.86	1	0.54	0.46
T × G	1	2.67	0.14	1	5.61	0.04	1	0.03	0.86	1	0.78	0.44	1	9.56	0.01	1	0.00	1.00
PFOA																		
Treatment (T)	1	126.95	2.86E-07	1	5.41	0.04	1	244.67	7.33E-09	1	194.36	2.46E-08	1	35.54	9.44E-05		na	
Genotype (G)	1	7.17	0.01	1	2.76	0.12	1	2.30	0.16	1	3.17	0.10	1	11.60	0.006		na	
T × G	1	1.17	0.39	1	2.76	0.12	1	0.26	0.62	1	1.66	0.22	1	0.73	0.41		na	
PFOS																		
Treatment (T)	1	124.55	6.68E-06	1	7.12	0.03	1	171.31	3.66E-07	1	165.48	4.25E-07	1	117.34	1.83E-06	1	4.56	0.03
Genotype (G)	1	4.00	6.45E-02	1	4.95	0.05	1	0.82	0.39	1	1.29	0.29	1	6.94	0.03	1	4.56	0.03
T × G	1	2.21	0.18	1	0.00	1.00	1	0.12	0.74	1	2.09	0.18	1	0.77	0.40	1	0.00	1.00
PET + PFOA																		
Treatment (T)	1	110.46	1.21E-07	1	6.40	0.03	1	579.63	3.37E-07	1	98.58	6.03E-05	1	6.51	0.04		na	
Genotype (G)	1	1.56	2.66E-01	1	0.40	0.54	1	3.21	0.12	1	0.22	0.65	1	0.00	1.00		na	
T × G	1	8.02	0.005	1	6.40	0.03	1	22.33	0.003	1	0.89	0.38	1	0.92	0.38		na	
PET + PFOS																		
Treatment (T)	1	29.05	8.17E-05	1	10.82	0.01	1	132.23	3.71E-05	1	69.56	0.0001	1	13.91	0.009	1	1.53	0.22
Genotype (G)	1	2.69	0.11	1	1.20	0.30	1	0.43	0.54	1	0.00	0.26	1	0.12	0.74	1	1.53	0.22
T × G	1	3.35	0.07	1	6.55	0.03	1	5.16	0.07	1	2.70	0.15	1	1.33	0.29	1	0.00	1.00
PFOA + PFOS																		
Treatment (T)	1	47.57	4.68E-06	1	2.45	0.17	1	95.90	4.49E-07	1	124.16	1.10E-07	1	157.64	2.92E-08		na	
Genotype (G)	1	16.46	0.0004	1	4.74	0.07	1	7.75	0.02	1	0.03	0.868743	1	106.91	2.49E-07		na	
T × G	1	4.31	0.032136	1	2.45	0.17	1	1.98	0.18	1	0.03	0.868743	1	66.00	3.21E-06		na	
PET + PFOA + PFOS																		
Treatment (T)	1	54.46	7.55E-05	1	17.54	0.00	1	14.27	0.009	1	99.46	0.0001	1	0.11	0.75	1	3.45	0.06
Genotype (G)	1	1.69	0.27	1	0.88	0.37	1	2.82	0.14	1	5.58	0.06	1	2.10	0.18	1	0.06	0.81
T × G	1	2.25	0.18	1	0.88	0.14	1	1.36	2.43E+26	1	4.07	0.10	1	1.37	0.27	1	0.00	1.00

Fig. 2. Phenotypic trajectory analysis. PTA on the *Daphnia magna* genotypes following chronic toxicity tests to three single chemicals (PET [50 mg/L], PFOA [7 ng/L], PFOS [70 ng/L] and their two-way and three-way mixtures). The multivariate response of five fitness-linked life history traits is shown. Open circles represent the control (nonexposed clonal replicates), and full circles represent the exposed clonal replicates. Genotype centroids are connected by reaction norms (solid lines), showing phenotypic change in direction and length. Difference among genotypes in terms of magnitude (M) and direction (Θ) of response are shown (s: significant, ns: non-significant). Genotypes are color-coded as in Fig. 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Univariate reaction norms. Univariate response of four fitness-linked life history traits between control and exposed *Daphnia* genotypes to single chemicals [PFOS (70 ng/L); PFOA (7 ng/L); PET (50 mg/L)] and two-way and tree-way mixtures. Size at maturity (mm), age at maturity (days), fecundity, interval between broods (time elapsed between the first two broods) are shown. Average and SD per genotype across four biological replicates are shown. Genotypes are color-coded as in Fig. 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

feeding impairment due to MPs filling the gut and direct toxic effects, which can be exacerbated in the presence of other persistent contaminants (Hodkovicova et al., 2022). Understanding the impact of MP on zooplankton, which are central to aquatic food webs, is crucial for assessing both direct toxicity and potential bioaccumulation throughout the food chain (Dai et al., 2022; de Sa et al., 2018). Our study, in alignment with existing results, revealed that part of the ingested microplastics is egested regularly (Frydkjaer et al., 2017). However, the adverse effect on ecological endpoints suggests that MP can be internalized (Guilhermino et al., 2021). Consequently, the adverse effects of MP on *Daphnia* manifest either directly by impeding food intake or indirectly by affecting fitness (Scherer et al., 2017). Prolonged exposure of *D. magna* to MP has been linked to juvenile mortality, smaller somatic growth, and delayed/reduced reproduction (Guilhermino et al., 2021; Ogonowski et al., 2016; Schur et al., 2023). Our findings validate prior research, showcasing a significant overall fitness impact of PET, evident through reduced fecundity and adult size, alongside increased mortality.

Studies on microplastic prevailingly use pristine spherical microplastic particles, and most investigate polystyrene (Funke et al., 2024).

Especially chronic toxicity studies have been limited to uniformly shaped commercial primary MPs (e.g., microbeads) (An et al., 2021), with only one study comparing toxicity of regularly shaped and irregular MP (Ogonowski et al., 2016). In our research, we opted for PET due to its widespread utilization in textiles, packaging, water, and air filters, leading to its discharge into surface water (Dhaka et al., 2022). Additionally, we incorporated irregularly shaped PET to better mirror conditions encountered by freshwater species in the natural environment. Irregularly shaped MP, particularly fibers, have been shown to exhibit higher toxicity compared to their regularly shaped counterparts (Funke et al., 2024; Ma et al., 2024; Rebelein et al., 2021). This heightened toxicity may be attributed to potential toxic or endocrine-disrupting additives, such as Bisphenol A, released as microplastics degrade into various shapes and sizes (An et al., 2021). Leachate from irregularly shaped MP was not quantified in our study, limiting our ability to conclude that additives may have contributed to the toxic response observed. Irregular MP are expelled at a slower rate than regularly shaped microplastics, potentially prolonging exposure within the digestive tract (Frydkjaer et al., 2017). In fact, irregularly shaped MP are

Fig. 4. Mixture chemicals effects. Empirical observation from single chemicals (a) and chemical mixtures (b) are shown per genotypes for four life history traits (age at maturity, size of maturity, fecundity and interval between broods). The predicted additive effects are shown as patterned bars and the observed effect as solid bars. The effects are synergistic when the effect of chemical mixtures is greater than the sum of the effects of individual chemicals; antagonistic when the effect of mixtures is smaller than the sum of the effects of individual chemicals; and additive when the effects of mixtures is equivalent to the sum of the individual effects. The statistics used to assess significant departure from the null model of additivity are in Table S3.

the most found in the tissue and guts of living organisms (de Sa et al., 2018).

Smaller MPs can be more toxic than larger ones due to their easier ingestion and prolonged retention in the digestive tract. In addition, smaller particles have a higher specific surface area, enabling them to adsorb greater amounts of persistent pollutants, such as perfluorinated compounds, compared to larger MP (Dai et al., 2022; Ribeiro et al., 2023; Yin et al., 2023). Previous studies have demonstrated that fragments and fibers are eliminated more slowly than regularly shaped MP. While spherical MP are typically egested within 24 h (An et al., 2021), our ingestion/egestion experiments show that nearly complete egestion of irregular particles and fibers requires at least 72 h. This longer residence time in the digestive tract, along with the increased potential for bioconcentration of irregularly shaped MP, can contribute to higher toxicity. Smaller particles can penetrate epithelial and cellular barriers, further contributing to their harmful effects (Frydkjaer et al., 2017).

4.2. Chemical mixtures effects

To date, the combined effects of PFOS and PFOA have predominantly been examined in human cell lines and vertebrates (e.g. Ding et al., 2013; Hu and Hu, 2009; Watanabe et al., 2009). The reported combined effects of these compounds range from additivity in human cell lines (Hu and Hu, 2009) to antagonistic interactions in prokaryotes (Rodea-Palomares et al., 2012), and a mix of synergistic and additive effects in fish embryos (Ding et al., 2013). Whereas the acute toxicity of PFOS and PFOA as single compounds have been tested in *Daphnia*, their combined effect has not been assessed, despite their frequent co-occurrence in aquatic environments. Our research represents a pioneering effort in quantifying the combined effects of PET and PFAS on the sentinel species *Daphnia* through the application of a null model of

additivity, adapted from ecological literature. This model enables to quantitatively assess synergistic, antagonistic and additive effects of multiple stressors (Cote et al., 2016). Our findings indicate that chemical mixtures involving two and three compounds exhibited 60% additive and 41% synergistic effects, with fecundity demonstrating entirely additive effects. These results corroborate meta-analyses suggesting that up to 50% of combined stressor effects in freshwater and marine environments are synergistic (Holmstrup et al., 2010). The significant level of additivity observed in our study underscores the critical need to understand the impacts of chemical mixtures on wildlife and human health. This highlights the necessity for incorporating toxicity assessments of unintentional mixtures into regulatory frameworks. Recent advances in untargeted approaches and machine learning algorithms make it feasible to uncover complex interactions between non-targeted fingerprinting of real-world chemical mixtures and their biological effects. Consequently, a revision of outdated toxicity assessment methodologies is both possible and imperative (Abdullahi et al., 2022a).

Our study is timely in addressing the combined effect of PFAS and MP, which commonly co-occur and whose presence in aquatic environments has significantly increased over the past 15 years (de Sa et al., 2018). Our results showing synergistic and additive effects of PFAS and MP could be explained by adsorption, which would align with literature evidence indicating that MP provide a substrate for the adsorption of other environmental contaminants [e.g. heavy metals (Ashton et al., 2010), and perfluorinated compounds (Dai et al., 2022; Ribeiro et al., 2023)]. However, because we did not measure sorption directly, we are not able to confirm this mechanism in our study. The compounded effects of microplastics and PFAS have been shown to be more severe for irregularly shaped microplastics, which may explain the more severe effect of mixtures on ecological endpoints observed in our study as compared to previous findings (Bhagwat et al., 2021). The higher impact

of mixtures can be explained by enhanced affinity due to the differing charges of the chemicals. For example, PFAS adsorb very effectively onto positively charged microplastics, whereas cationic PFAS and negatively charged microplastics exhibit high affinity (Dai et al., 2022). This may be compounded by biofilm formation on the microplastic surface, which can generate a chemosensory response, rendering the microplastics bioavailable and palatable for ingestion by wildlife, thereby leading to bioaccumulation across the food web (Vroom et al., 2017). It is possible that the increased toxicity of mixtures involving PET in our study may be partially due to reduced feeding abilities in *Daphnia*. However, if starvation was the primary factor responsible for higher toxicity, we would expect a significantly smaller size at maturity only in the exposures involving PET. Conversely, we observed a significant reduction in somatic growth across all exposures, suggesting that factors beyond feeding impairment are contributing to the toxic effect of mixture involving MP.

4.3. Genotype-specific toxic response is determined by previous exposure to chemical stress

In contrast to conventional ecotoxicological studies, which frequently utilize a single commercially available *Daphnia* strain, we employed two genotypes with distinct histories of exposure to chemical pollutants. This approach allowed us to discern genotype-specific effects of PET on age at maturity and intervals between asexual reproductions. We also observed genotype-specific effects in the PFOS and the PFOS + PFOA exposures. However, in the three-way exposure, only size at maturity exhibited a significant genotype-by-treatment interaction.

In all instances where genotype-specific effects were identified, the genotype with historical exposure to chemical stress experienced the greatest fitness costs, except for mortality rates, which were higher for the naïve genotype for both PFOS and PET exposures. These findings corroborate previous studies indicating that *Daphnia* genotypes naïve to chemical stress exhibit greater tolerance to novel chemical stress, whereas genotypes with a history of chemical exposure demonstrate reduced tolerance to new chemicals (Abdullahi et al., 2023; Abdullahi et al., 2022b; Gigl et al., 2024; Noyes et al., 2009). This reduced tolerance is likely due to cumulative fitness costs accrued from prior exposures, leading to compromised resilience when encountering new chemical challenges. Our study and few others using multiple genotypes emphasizes the critical need to consider genetic diversity and historical exposure in ecotoxicological assessments. The observed genotype-specific responses highlight the complex interplay between genetic background and pollutant exposure, underscoring the importance of incorporating multiple genotypes in environmental risk assessments to accurately predict the ecological impact of chemical pollutants.

5. Conclusions

The current study elucidates the effects of PFAS and MP and quantifies the mechanisms of their mixtures using an additivity model derived from ecological literature. The assessment focused on fitness-related endpoints, revealing significant impacts on fecundity and age at maturity. Specifically, we observed a markedly reduced number of offspring coupled with developmental failure, leading to egg abortion within the brood pouch. Mortality rates increased in treatments involving PFOS and PET. These results coupled with molecular signatures of gene and metabolite dysregulation can reveal the underpinning mechanisms of toxicity of chemical mixtures involving chemicals of very high concern. By using the functional conservation of genes and metabolites across species, it is possible to identify toxicity targets in other species, guiding *in vivo* and *in vitro* validation of toxic effects in human models, fully exploiting *Daphnia* as a sentinel species (Abdullahi et al., 2022a).

Due to the exceptional surface-active and resilience properties of

PFAS, manufacturers have rapidly adopted new alternatives or next-generation PFAS to replace restricted compounds such as PFOS and PFOA. These alternatives often resemble some byproducts of longer-chain PFAS. Although the toxic effects of these new PFAS remain largely unknown, emerging studies suggest that they likely possess similar toxic profiles as long-chain PFAS (Coperchini et al., 2020; Ragnarsdottir et al., 2024). Consequently, it is imperative to continue investigating the toxicological impacts of these substances on wildlife to inform regulatory and conservation efforts.

Our study provides critical insights into the chronic toxicity of PFAS and MP on the ecological endpoints of the sentinel species *Daphnia*. In addition, we quantify the combine effect of these chemicals on ecological endpoints, revealing synergistic and additive effects. This research significantly advances the understanding of the toxicity of these chemicals of high concern for environmental and human health.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tayebeh Soltanighias: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Abubakar Umar:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Muhammad Abdullahi:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mohamed Abou-Elwafa Abdallah:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Luisa Orsini:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Notes

The authors declare no conflicting interests.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

We thank Chantal Jackson for the artwork of Fig. 1. This work was funded by the Horizon Europe HORIZON-IA project UPSTREAM (101112877). The results and conclusions reflect only the author's view, and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. AU is supported by the Petroleum Technology Development Fund, Nigeria (PTDF/ED/OSS/PHD/AU/1862/2020PHD169). TS is supported by a PhD scholarship from Aston University, Birmingham, UK. The authors acknowledge Dr Oddný Ragnarsdóttir for her support with the PFAS analysis.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2024.125133>.

Data availability

The fitness linked life history data from the laboratory exposures can be found at the dryad entry: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.51c59zwh6>.

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